

Counselling Approaches to Skill Acquisition Among Adolescents

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Abstract

This paper discussed counselling approaches for skills acquisition among adolescents. Skills acquisition education is vital at all levels of education. This is backed by the critical role that science and technology play in any nation's progress. Science and technology skills can be learned by adolescents. They are frequently involved in daily tasks that necessitate the use of scientific and technological skills. Counselling approaches for skills acquisition among adolescents should be taught and learned, as well as the abilities that should be obtained through appropriate exposure to connected and right situations. Three group career guidance and counselling methods are to be used for effective and improvement of career maturity and decision-making skills among the adolescents. There are acceptable approaches to teaching competence, whether as a process or as a manipulation, for science and technology trainers or teachers. Knowing the best strategy to take, the mistakes to avoid, the tactics for motivating skill learners, the skills to teach, and the best ways to assist learners practice the skills they have learnt is key to success in teaching skill. This will go a long way toward putting adolescents to work and assisting in the development and answers to some of the society's challenges. It is recommended that; group career guidance and counselling should be provided to help adolescents in schools to acquire skills in career maturity. Career counselling should be made compulsory for secondary and tertiary schools and included in the nation's secondary school curriculum. School authority should allow the trained school counsellor to carry out group work among the students since they are the personnel equipped with strategies for behaviour change and modification. Finally, it is necessary to decentralize all efforts meant for entrepreneurial development in such a way that local government areas would be empowered to carry out such responsibilities.

Keywords: Counselling, Skill acquisition, Cognitive abilities, educational abilities.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, youth restiveness has become a hot topic for discussion in the social, economic, and political realms. It is a fact that a restive youth population in Niger State will prevent the state from thriving and progressing significantly. Because of the frequency of this problem, Nigeria's peace, security, and corporate existence as a nation are jeopardized. Unemployment, a lack of basic and inadequate infrastructure, and poor social amenities are among the causes of youth restlessness, as are a lack of technical skills to engage them in becoming self-reliant. Technical abilities serve as the foundation for future science teaching and learning at all levels of education. The low number of autonomous or self-sufficient adolescents in science and technology from higher education institutions indicates that there are little or no skills teaching in science and technology, which has raised a lot of concern. Science and technology are constantly reducing the world to a global village. As a result, it is necessary to mobilize as many youngsters as possible, as well as teachers, to learn and impart science skills.

Youth is a stage of transition from youthful dependence to adulthood's freedom and awareness of the necessity to collaborate with other members of society to attain the society's goals and objectives (UNESCO 2017). At this point, both educated and uneducated youths are determined to find long-term jobs to assist them meet

their basic necessities. However, the percentage of youth in society is growing, resulting in higher unemployment rates and a higher level of dependency. It is critical to emphasize that youths' strength, labor, and efforts are valuable assets in a healthy social environment. Positive contributions aid in a location's growth and development. Youth has a crucial role in any culture (Akosah-Twumasi, Emeto, Lindsay, Tsey, Malau-Aduli, 2018).

Youths play a variety of roles, including maintaining law and order, preserving societal culture, promoting knowledge, participating in communal politics, developing projects, attending cultural festivals, participating in local sports events, and participating in traditional marriages and funerals, among others (Ikpa and Igbo 2022). The restlessness of adolescents has resulted in their incapacity to solve problems, efficiently fulfill tasks, and meet societal goals. As a result, kidnapping, vandalism of oil pipelines, an increase in armed robbery, bomb assaults, thuggery, murder, property destruction, increased insecurity, and crude oil theft (bunkering), to name a few, have become commonplace among adolescents (Anho, 2021). All of the aforementioned crimes are inextricably linked to a lack of employable technical abilities that young people are supposed to possess. The acquisition of technical skills has long been recognized as critical to the human

race's survival and progress (Brewer, 2013). The importance of science and technology in the educational process backs up this notion. At all levels, science and technology are integrated into all nations' educational systems. There are appropriate techniques for acquiring skills in these fields of information as bodies of knowledge. The Nigerian government, through its education policy, strongly encourages the teaching and learning of science and technology in primary schools (Nbina, 2019).

The National Policy on Education's provisions for primary education (2012) specifically state the following objectives: Create a solid foundation for scientific and critical thinking. Provide opportunities for the youth to develop manipulative abilities that will enable him to function effectively in society within his limitations. Provide the youth with the necessary tools for further study, including preparation for local trades and crafts. The government has mandated that the following disciplines be included in the primary school curriculum in order to interpret the aims related to scientific and technological endeavours. Science, which can be interpreted as primary science, integrated science, general science, or simply science; Mathematics, which aids in the development of reflective thinking; Physical and Health Education, which promotes the development of a healthy mind and body; Agriculture/Home Economics, which can be viewed as an applied science that easily relates to the child's immediate society; Cultural and Creative Arts, which include drawing and handicrafts, among other things, as a means of preparing the child for the future; These two endeavors are commonly referred to as local crafts, and are viewed as one of the foundations for technology at this level of schooling (OECD, 2016).

Promoting the career-decision making skills of students in secondary school is one of the cardinal goals of school career guidance. Brewer, (2022). Identified the goal of facilitating career decision as the unifying theme among various career guidance approaches. The need for career decision making is very prevalent in the human lives. The democratic nature of Nigeria society coupled with the increasing complexity of schools and labour market system often confront the adolescents with unlimited array of educational and career options. The school owes the students the responsibility of providing specialized assistance through the school counselling programme for career decision making. A variety of approaches to career decision making exists

in the various therapeutic models of career guidance but this paper is out to contribute to the existed techniques so as to meet the present situation of over dependent of Nigerian graduates of secondary school on government employment. It is noted as observed that students in the nation's secondary schools are always facing with problems of career choice toward the tail end of their secondary school education. It is of the opinion of this paper to stress the importance of career programme which is to be organised in schools especially toward the end of Junior Secondary School or at the starting point of Senior Secondary School level so as to facilitate in the students the idea of career readiness that will eventually transform to career decision making of all these students. And for this to be accomplished, there is need for a program like group guidance and counselling to be sponsored by the school administrators in collaboration with the school guidance counsellor on career planning, at least once in a year for the students in the senior secondary school level. Since the problem of career decision making appeared to be a general problem among the Nigeria youths, the group guidance and counselling strategies as used in the work seem to the researcher as appropriate technique to embark upon by the school counsellor to facilitate career maturity. This point was buttressed by Iaccarino, (2017) who asserted then that among the various type of group work available, the most important to the Nigerian counsellors is group counseling for vocational exploration. Addis Ababa, (2017). Also remarked on the group as a medium for helping individual and the readiness to work in group will help in fostering vocational maturity among secondary school students.

Counseling through groups was a programme designed as an introductory experience for preparing students or youths to work with various groups. The process turns the foundation for the understanding of group process and acquisition of basic skills in human relations, effective communication and overall leadership skills necessary for working with various groups.

Concept of Counselling

Counselling psychology is a psychological specialty that began with a focus on vocational counselling, but later moved its emphasis to adjustment counseling, and then expanded to cover all normal psychology and psychotherapy. Vocational counselling (sometimes referred to as vocational rehabilitation) is a service for developing skills to find employment (Udo, (2012).

Those born or suffering from cognitive or physical impairments due to injuries can leverage vocational counselling to learn how to enter or reenter the workforce while taking into account their limitations.

Vocational counselling usually takes place in different facilities, including government training facilities, community centers, vocational training centers, along with colleges and schools. It can also be performed at a job site that has a supportive work program. A vocational expert may accompany a potential employee to a work site to assess the work environment and offer supervision. Typically, the process starts after the vocational expert assesses the medical records, cognitive abilities, and physical limitations. That way, they can determine all the factors that affect the person's capacity to maintain a job. (Ekpenyong, 2019). In other words, vocational counseling helps individuals find and enter a field that is within their area of interest and scope of their capabilities. For those who can't perform in their previous job due to their disability, a vocational counsellor can help find return-to-work options, which may include job modification. If that is not possible, the counsellor will assess the individual's ability to enter a new line of work or find any positions they he or she may be able to perform with additional training. When asking what vocational counseling is, you also have to consider what it includes. Typically, it's focused on improving workplace skills, which includes:

1. Determining interests and aptitudes
2. Determining cognitive and physical abilities
3. Identifying any adaptive equipment that may help an individual find employment
4. Accommodating the workplace equipment or environment
5. Finding the appropriate training programs
6. Evaluating performance

Skills

A skill is the learned ability to act with determined results with good execution often within a given amount of time, energy, or both. Skills can often be divided into domain-general and domain-specific skills.

For example, in the domain of work, some general skills would include time management, teamwork and leadership, self-motivation and others, whereas domain-specific skills would be used only for a certain job. Skill usually requires certain environmental stimuli and situations to assess the level of skill being shown and used.

A skill may be called an art when it represents a body of knowledge or branch of learning, as in the art of medicine or the art of war. Although the arts are also skills, there are many skills that form an art but have no connection to the fine arts.

People need a broad range of skills to contribute to the modern economy. A joint ASTD and U.S. Department of Labor study showed that through technology, the workplace is changing, and identified 16 basic skills that employees must have to be able to change with it (Udo, (2017). Three broad categories of skills are suggested and these are technical, human, and conceptual. The first two can be substituted with hard and soft skills, respectively.

Skills Acquisition

Skill acquisition is the interdisciplinary science specific to the knowledge of and about voluntary control over body segments and joint movements to solve a motor skill. Referred to as motor learning and control, it also deals in calibration, action, perception, and intention of the environment-performer relationship.

The concept of skill education and skill acquisition is essential as it has become an avenue to understand how the neuromuscular system functions to coordinate as well as activate the limbs and muscles that are involved directly in the motor skill performance. Many skill acquisition theories are floating across the world, and amongst them, the motor learning theory by Fitts and Posner is considered the best (Okorie, And Ezeji (2019). The truth of the matter is that it has evolved and is now described as an interpretation of the brain-behavior relationship. Memory and thinking have been linked with motor learning , control and performances. Especially early learning is about a genuine attempt by the learner to understand the basic pattern of coordination and movement. The learner has to use verbal and cognitive processes to solve problems and achieve desired goals.

The motor learning theory by Fitts and Posner is a three-stage theory that was released in the late 1900s

(Osuala, (2020). This is a simple paradigm that has proved extremely useful in understanding, accelerating, and improving the process of motor learning and skill acquisition. The various stages of motor learning and their implications in the field of effective coaching are described below-

Stage 1: Cognitive Stage

The first stage of Fitts and Posner's three-stage theory is known as the cognitive stage. Here the learner will put his focus on things that need to be done. Questions like what to do are essential in this stage; for example, a lawn tennis player will ask what should be the length of my serves to maintain that perfect length. To accomplish his purpose, the player will pay attention to what his coach has to say. In the cognitive stage, the learner tries to learn a skill by receiving verbal or visual knowledge. The feedback matters and that is why he will be paying close attention to his instructions that include information related to errors he has been making and his lack of consistency. This stage of motor learning and control is also known as the verbal motor stage, as verbal feedback plays an essential role in achieving desired results. Osuala, (2020), stated that the cognitive stage begins by understanding what to do and is all about processing the related information. It involves verbal conveyance and acquisition or cognition of new information. In the example mentioned above, the coach is the key to achieve large gains as he tries to make the feedback look like a cognitive task and not mechanical intervention.

The player could have discovered how to perform his services, but it would have taken him long hours of practice before he would be able to get a grip on it. The trial and error, experimentations, and creative learning, along with problem-solving skills, would have proved helpful, but it would have been a long-drawn-out process.

On the other hand, the feedback by the coach is merely acquiring information from an expert and doing things accordingly to save time and achieve goals. Arogundade (2019), this is why the cognitive stage is essential because, in this stage, an individual tries to process information to cognitively understand the

parameters, needs, and requirements of motor movement.

Stage 2: Associative Stage

The second stage of Fitts and Posner's three-stage theory is the associative stage. Essential characteristics of this stage are less information in the verbal format, conscious performance, little gains in the performance graph, awkward movement, making adjustments, and taking a long time to complete tasks. This is the stage where the learner starts improving his performances after lots of practice. He associates specific cues with the motor problems he faces and tries to act accordingly to solve them. The fundamental has already been established, and now is the time for improvements and refinement. In the associative stage, the learner puts lots of conscious effort into body movements to decrease performance variability. The name Motor stage also knows the associative stage because the issue is about learning how to perform the skill. The learner puts his onus on making adjustments in his movements and skills. If you look from the cognitive perspective, the learner has now shifted his focus from what to do to how to do and is making constructive attempts to transfer the declarative information into procedural knowledge.

None of the athletes in the world will be able to perform a perfect ten score every time they play. It is an undisputed claim that there is always room for improvement even when you are at your best. This is applicable for every type of sport; for example, a tennis player will try to improve his serves for an ace, a basketball player can improve his shooting technique, a softball player can enhance his pitching style, and a swimmer can improve his stroke, etc. The sign of a successful player and his coach is that both of them are always on the look-out for making further improvements and getting better.

Stage 3: Autonomous Stage

The third stage of Fitts and Posner's three-stage theory is the autonomous stage.

This is the stage where the player has gained information and practicing diligently has become automatic. The learner can accomplish it without any

conscious thought as it has become ingrained in his movements.

This stage of the motor learning paradigm takes years of hard work and training. It is reserved exclusively for elite players whose motor performance has become habitual and whose cognitive process is minimal. In this stage, a player is capable of attending and processing information at the same time. The phase where thinking things is less and response is automatic and looks like just a state of natural flow without any undue effort. Self-learning plays an integral part in the autonomous stage as skilled performers can identify errors and make adjustments accordingly by themselves. It is a fact that not many players reach the third stage. It is the instructions, practice structure, and the task variables that help to determine whether a player will be able to achieve the autonomous stage or not.

There are both good and bad case scenarios and outcomes associated with an autonomous stage. The good about this phase is that it requires less cognitive demands, less effort, and less attention, and thus the player is mentally free to pursue another task at the same time without losing concentration. For example, a mathematician will continue to solve a high-end problem while listening to music without a negative impact on either of the activities.

Approaches for Skills Acquisition

There are a variety of approaches for skills acquisition that can lead to the acquisition of associated skills in adolescent education. In this context, we have already mentioned the need of a learner-centered approach. Another method for developing abilities is problem-solving. The relevance of science and technology is highlighted in this context, and technological principles will be taught in science classes.

According to Samaniego, Gonzalo, Esteve-González and Vaca (2015) science and technical skill provides a roadmap for achieving scientific and technological literacy by emphasizing individuals' responsible decisions in the real world of science and technology. Developing the ability to think critically about and analyze events in society using techno-scientific methodologies; Anjum (2020) has identified eleven characteristics of programs that highlight the priority of

instruction above curricular content. The emphasis on process skills, which students may utilize in their own issue solving, is a very relevant and vital characteristic. The approach should not be considered without reference to the program's features (Bob, David and Stephen, 2019) and its effective implementation in scientific teaching has been urged to focus on five factors: Learner friendly environment; Inventiveness; Learner-centered method; Problem-solving focus; Useful resource organization Teachers must create settings where students will need the essential concepts and process abilities in order to effectively employ the approach in science instruction. Students' learning abilities are stimulated in this way, and this sort of learning is consistent with the Constructivist Learning Model (Shah, 2019). The model explains that knowledge is never independent of the observer. It necessitates: a personal commitment to question; a personal commitment to explain and test explanations for validity; and each learner's ability to piece together concepts and structures that have personal meaning in order for learning to occur. According to Joseph and Lawrence (2016) using the constructive model effectively entails using teaching strategies that include the following specific procedures:

1. Planning activities, which include identifying and using students' questions and ideas to guide lessons and entire instructional units, accepting and encouraging students' initiative, and promoting students' leadership, collaboration, information retrieval, and action as a result of the learning process.
2. Classroom methods, such as incorporating students' ideas, experiences, and interests into courses; encouraging the use of alternate sources of information, such as written materials and live experts; and asking open-ended questions;
3. Students' activities, which include encouraging students to expound on their questions and responses, suggesting causes for events and circumstances, and putting their own views to the test. For example, answering their queries and speculating on the cause, as well as anticipating specific outcomes;
4. Teaching technique, which includes seeking answers to students' ideas before presenting teacher ideas or studying ideas from other textbooks or sources; encouraging students to

challenge each other's conceptualizations and ideas; and using cooperative learning strategies that emphasize collaboration, individuality, and division of labour tactics.

Allowing sufficient time for reflection and analysis; appreciating and using all ideas generated by pupils; and fostering self-examination of real evidence to support views; and reforming beliefs in light of fresh experience and evidence.

Constructivist professors categorize these tactics into four groups:

- i. Invitation, which entails observing one's environment for points of interest, as well as asking questions, considering possible responses to questions, noting unusual phenomena, and identifying circumstances in which student perspectives differ.
- ii. Exploration, which is engaging in concentrated play to explore various alternatives, gather and organize data, look for information, experiment with materials, observe specific phenomena, construct a model, and brainstorm possible alternatives use problem-solving tactics, choose relevant resources, discuss solutions with others, evaluate options, debate issues, identify risks and implications, set investigation parameters, and analyze data
- iii. Taking action, such as making decisions, applying knowledge and skills, transferring knowledge and skills, sharing information and ideas, asking new questions, developing products, and promoting ideas, by communicating information and ideas, constructing and explaining a model, constructing a new explanation, reviewing and critiquing solutions, determining appropriate closure, and integrating a solution with existing knowledge and experience.

Counseling Approaches for Skills Acquisition Among Adolescents

Group counselling, the strategies and skills provides on in depth look at group counselling with an emphasis on practical knowledge and techniques for effective group leadership. Consequently, the National Educational Policy document (2004) states that the Nation's educational activity should be centred on the students in order for them to acquire maximum skills acquisition for self-development and fulfillment in the labour

market. Regrettably, due to some barriers, the level of practical skills acquired by these adolescents, compared with the demands of the labour market and technological advancement, is nothing to talk about.

Consequently, most adolescent graduates of universities in Nigeria are without gainful employment. Worst still, these graduates too are unable to establish their entrepreneurial skills ventures because they would not be able to put into practice what they studied in their tertiary institution since such skills were poorly acquired.

Indeed, university is defined as that education that provides skills, knowledge, competencies and attitudes necessary for effective employment in specific business occupations. According Udo (2008) university is a comprehensive activity-based educational programme that is concerned with the acquisition of practical skills, understandings, attitudes, work habits and competencies that are requisite to success in a chosen business occupation while skill is defined by Ekpenyong (1988) as the ability to use one's knowledge effectively and readily in execution of performance; technical expertness, a power or habit of doing any particular thing competently. He opined that this definition is stressing that a skill is based on using knowledge expertly; the objective of which is to bring that knowledge to maximum level of competency. Hence maximum skills acquisition involves that ability to perform any given tasks with ease, competently and expertly without much stress and sweat.

On the other hand, impediments refer to barriers, hindrances and obstructions to maximum skills acquisition for adolescents in tertiary institutions programme.

Coselling therefore, aims at helping students make right choice of career with the result that they are happy useful to themselves and the society in which they live. Career guidance, therefore was designed to provide prior to train students for skills acquisition maturity and decision making. Iaccarino (2017) holds the opinion that students should be assisted to have realistic career orientations. The basic aim of counsellors in school is to encourage students to grow and realize their full potentials in skills acquisition. Career counselling therefore, is to assist the students at individual level or group in integrating the information about himself and the world of work and to have a plan for skills acquisition. This involves a face-to-face encounter between the facilitator or counsellor and the client. The

student is assisted before any occupational selection and adjustment. Arogundade (2019) emphasized that vocational counselling is a need that is not properly handled by the career teachers and the school guidance counsellors.

Therefore bridge the gap between theory and practice with Counselling and the combination of the two approaches to counselling, for a set of students in senior secondary school for career choice and decision making skills. Everyman is expected to take to one occupation or another in pursuit of livelihood, satisfaction and contribution to the up-keep of the society.

The uncertainty that surrounds some skill performance is removed when the theory that drives the performance is linked to actual practice. This allows learners to accept that they can do it. The learner's understanding and willingness to practice grows when the teacher makes the facts, the idea, and the relationship of the theory to the practice plain to them.

- i. Learners of skill develop a need to study in a practice environment that reflects their actual job situation. The environment in which a skill is taught is similar to the one in which the learner will encounter in the workplace.
- ii. Production jobs, not phantom employment, are used to incentivize youths. Learners will put out all of their effort to master a skill that will result in the creation of an article that they will see and likely use in their homes and other locations.
- iii. If learners are given appropriate explanation and knowledge about what they are to learn, the teacher has a high success rate in teaching them to acquire skill. It is not enough to show competency in a skill; trainees should be instructed when and when they can apply it.

Importance of Skill Acquisition in Nigeria

According to Okorie and Ezeji (2019) the acquisition of the requisite skills is a means of increasing the productive power of any nations. Consequently, they added that the Nigerian society should recognize the fact that every citizen should be equipped to contribute effectively to the welfare of the country. The acquisition of such practical skills is important because when efficient and skilful hands are employed in any

field of human endeavours, high productivity is usually achieved. Economically, maximum skills acquisition by VBE students and others will help to enrich the Nigerian society and in this way, tend to make possible sustainable development.

Okorie and Ezeji (2019) opined that a rich nation is one that is capable of meeting the economic, social, moral and political needs of the citizenry. Nigeria as a nation will enjoy sustainable development if adolescent in particular and all other students in general acquire maximum skills acquisition and competencies in their specialties. Furthermore, politically, practical skills acquisition tends to promote personal and national greatness. They also pointed out that the behaviour of an individual in a society or the behaviour of a nation in a community of nations may be influenced by the skills and competencies possessed by that individual or nation.

Socially, the acquisition of maximum skills helps a person to provide amusement, happiness, love, affection and enjoyment to other individuals as well as the entire nation at large. It also helps to reduce criminal activities such as armed robbery, kidnapping, and other social vices among the youths. To the adolescent, maximum skills acquisition helps them to be engaged in productive work either for themselves or for employers of labour.

This enables adolescent to qualify for and hold productive employment as well as increases their productivity and earns more remuneration. Other importance of acquiring maximum skills and competencies includes, the following: it reduces the drop-out rates among the Nigerian youths, it helps to make the youths intelligent users of the products of technology as well as the most reliable vehicle for economic prosperity and diplomatic supremacy of the Nigeria nation. These benefits of maximum skills acquisition are still there if adolescent will think twice and change their negative attitudes towards it and turn to develop themselves sufficiently in the skills and competencies inherent in adolescent programmes of their institutions. In fact when adolescent fail to acquire maximum skills from the programme; this in turn affects sustainable development negatively.

Nigeria's Technical Skills Acquisition Challenges

The foundation for the rest of the educational system is the primary level of education. Nigeria's search for scientific and technological advancements; Breakthroughs can only be achieved if primary school students are taught to have a positive attitude toward science; the following procedures can be taken to archive this: In primary schools, only National Certificate of Education (NCE) graduates in the basic sciences should teach science, followed by in-service training; All primary schools should have a science laboratory where student can interact with scientific objects; Curriculum reform is required, with both the content and approach of the existing curriculum being examined; Primary schools should have a computer laboratory to help students build computer appreciation abilities. Science teachers in primary and secondary schools need to expand their knowledge of science. Primary school science instructors require good and ongoing professional development.

Recognize that, within the context of education, science and technology include human progress toward a more wealthy and equitable future. It is necessary to recognize that global science and technology networks serve as a platform for bringing together relevant social and professional communities in order to facilitate the expansion of concerted international collaboration in order to effectively address the challenges of scientific and technological skills acquisition. The government must generate the political will to address educational issues in general, as well as the issue of teachers and professional development for teachers in particular. An effective teacher has the same right to a reasonable income and working conditions as a civil servant with the same or similar qualifications and experience. This will allow him to properly carry out his responsibilities.

CONCLUSION

This paper discussed counseling approaches for skills acquisition among adolescents. Skills acquisition education is vital at all levels of education. This is backed by the critical role that science and technology play in any nation's progress. Science and technology skills can be learned by youths. Adolescents are frequently involved in daily tasks that necessitate the use of scientific and technological skills. Counseling approaches for skills acquisition among adolescents should be taught and learned, as well as the abilities

that should be obtained through appropriate exposure to connected and right situations.

Conclusively, the counselling approaches were effective to improve the career maturity and decision-making skills among the secondary school students. There are acceptable approaches to teaching competence, whether as a process or as a manipulation, for science and technology teachers. Knowing the best strategy to take, the mistakes to avoid, the tactics for motivating skill learners, the skills to teach, and the best ways to assist learners practice the skills they have learnt is key to success in teaching skill. This will go a long way toward putting young people to work and assisting in the development of answers to some of the society's challenges.

Any of the three guidance is able to help in the improvement of career maturity and decision making skills, but group career counseling combined counselling is the most effective therapy for career maturity and decision making skills for students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that,

1. Counseling should be provided to help students acquire skills in career maturity.
2. Counseling should be made compulsory for secondary and tertiary schools and included in the nation's secondary school curriculum.
3. Establishment of more VBE skill acquisition business centres, where VBE students could go and acquire skills of typewriting, shorthand, accounting, marketing, salesmanship, etc. 2. All facilities and equipment required for the business occupations are to be put in place in order to enhance training in all the business skills.
4. Guidance and counselling units should be put in place in all the business centres and technical colleges so as to create career awareness to the trainees.
5. Teachers of VBE departments should be trained and retrained so that they will update their training to fill the gap between school training and the establishment of functional skill acquisition business centres for intensive and extensive practice before graduation and

6. Establishment of a special scheme whereby interested university graduates will be supplied with a take up equipment and loan to enable them start their own skill acquisition business centres.
7. School authority should allow the trained school counselor to carry out group work among the students since they are the personnel equipped with strategies for behaviour change and modification.
8. In order to ensure the effectiveness of all efforts geared towards promoting entrepreneurial development, it is recommended that proactive measures must be made to prevent and remove corruption plaguing the system. All funds meant for entrepreneurial development must be transparently administered and proper channels of accountability must be established for the system.
9. There is no gainsaying the fact that if corruption is effectively tackled, Nigeria will make a breakthrough in her entrepreneurial development efforts. Moreover, periodic workshops and seminars on entrepreneurial development should be organized for school leavers and young graduates.
10. The National Directorate of Employment should be empowered in terms of capital and legal framework to be able to organize such training free of charge for the teeming unemployed youth in the country. All necessary legal frameworks must also be put in place to ensure transparency and accountability on the part of the directorate.
11. Finally, it is necessary to decentralize all efforts meant for entrepreneurial development in such a way that local government areas would be empowered to carry out such responsibilities.
12. Funds meant for entrepreneurial development should be disbursed to appropriate agencies which must have visible and effective presence at the local government, community and school levels. It is hoped that effective implementation of these recommendations would help in fostering entrepreneurial development in the country.

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